

Social inclusion through the urban lens: a comparative analysis of neighbourhoods of residential racial homogeneity and heterogeneity in Cape Town, South Africa.

Ruth Nelson^{*1}

¹Department of Multi-Actor Systems, Faculty of Technology, Policy and Management, TU Delft

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Summary

This article proposes the development of a data driven framework for examining urban social inclusion through the profiling of neighbourhoods by combining spatial network measurements, transport, land use and socio-economic indicators in Cape Town, the oldest city in South Africa. Neighbourhoods are considered important spatial units within cities and have strong social and cultural connotations. The results show that neighbourhoods with increased residential racial heterogeneity have access to higher levels of mixed land use, transport, and global closeness centrality. Furthermore, neither extremely high nor low-income neighbourhoods are related to racial heterogeneity. The results enable the identification of structural barriers that perpetuate social exclusion. It is envisioned that this approach could support policy makers and urban planners within decision making processes.

KEYWORDS:

Social inclusion, neighbourhoods, spatial network, racial heterogeneity

1. Introduction

The United Nation's Sustainable Development Goals have deemed inclusive, resilient, and sustainable cities as global imperatives. Despite wide recognition and commitment, building inclusive cities remains a challenge. Many studies of social inclusion are traditionally conducted at an individual or household scale, with little emphasis on the interaction between human dynamics and the spatial configuration of cities. The novelty of this paper lies within the proposal of examining social inclusion explicitly through the lens of urbanity based on readily available open access data sets. The neighbourhood is chosen as the principal component of analysis as it is theorised as both an important spatial unit and social construct. Relations between multidimensional indicators are explored through well recognised approaches in data analytics, principally employing the unsupervised classification algorithm, k-means clustering. The results reveal insights into factors that perpetuate social exclusion, through highlighting properties of the urban realm which may support or hinder a community's capability to meaningfully participate. Furthermore, they illustrate that there are significant differences between neighbourhood typologies.

The primary question that will be addressed in this article is: *what is the relationship between regional spatial inequalities associated with social exclusion and demographically residentially racially heterogenous neighbourhoods?*

2. Social inclusion through an urban lens

2.1 Setting the urban context

The current state of global urban development is highlighted by the *United Nations World Social Report*

* R.j.nelson@tudelft.nl

(2020) which documents vast global inequalities. Graham and Marvin (2001) show how the contemporary global premium networked spaces primarily connect the wealthy, perpetuating polarisation. Within South Africa, the persistence of produced, distorted settlement patterns characterized by segregation is well documented (Parnell and Robinson, 2012, State of South African Cities Report, 2016).

2.2 Linking social inclusion with accessibility

Social inclusion can be thought of as the ability to access resources, goods, and services and to participate in normal relationships and activities (Levitass et al, 2007:9). Whilst, reaching opportunities becomes more than a function of how they are distributed in space (Pereira et al, 2017), understanding where those opportunities exist and how access to them may be restricted or enhanced is an important step.

Within space syntax theory, the city is articulated as a relational network. As Hillier (1996) proposes through the theory of natural movement, the spatial network of the street layout produces attraction inequalities, which generate or restrict co-presence. The notion of a dual grid structure composed of foreground and background network is developed (Hillier and Netto, 2002). The foreground network generates movement, maximizing co-presence through connectivity, attracting movement rich land use, whereas the background network is conservative, minimizing co-presence, reinforcing socio-cultural stability. Public space offers capacity for bringing socially distant people together and even if this does not lead to direct interaction, it has an impact on segregation (Legeby, 2013). Church et al. (2000) emphasizes that factors which inhibit accessibility tend not to appear in isolation and are embedded within specific geographical contexts. Geographical morphological barriers such as railroads and rivers are shown to correlate with social network fragmentation (Toth et al, 2021). Oviedo (2021) notes in his review of urban form in Latin America, that areas of economic activity tend to be far from where most low-income populations reside, leading to a form of “spatial mismatch”. Distribution effects in cities do have an impact on social exclusion (Van Wee and Geurs, 2011). There are direct links between social inclusion and accessibility (Lucas, 2012).

2.3 Measuring social exclusion: a neighbourhood focused approach

Neighbourhoods are important determinants of the quantity and quality of human behaviour; they play an important role in mediating both economic, political and individual processes (Sampson, 2019:7). Many urban design models primarily focus on the neighbourhood, such as the *Garden City* by Ebenezer Howard. Within the social sciences, there are also multiple conceptualisations of the neighbourhood such as the Ethnic Enclave and the Ghetto (Peach, 2001). Clustering analysis is applied to several neighbourhood studies which show that this method for developing neighbourhood types is robust (Delmelle, 2016).

3. Datasets and methods

The research requires a methodological approach that can encompass both physical and behavioural aspects to shed light on the relationship between the spatial configuration of neighbourhoods, social inclusion, and racial integration. South African National Census data (2011) is aggregated to the scale of the neighbourhood which is defined by the administrative boundary lines. Spatial data is primarily gleaned from the [City of Cape Town's Open Data Portal](#). The data is normalised and inputted into the K-means clustering algorithm, which enables the identification of various categories of neighbourhoods. The optimal number of clusters are identified using the Silhouette Score.

The approach focuses on four dimensions:

Socio-economic factors

The mean income is calculated for each adult person in a neighbourhood from Census data.

The Neighbourhood Diversity Index (ND Index), developed by Michael Maly (2000), is employed as a measure of demographic racial heterogeneity. It is important to note that *Coloured*, refers to Mixed Race and is not derogatory in South Africa.

ND Index:

$$ND = (C_w - T_w) + (C_b - T_b) + (C_c - T_c) + (C_i - T_i) + (C_o - T_o)$$

- C_w = city percentage: White (16%)
- C_b = city percentage: Black (39%)
- C_c = city percentage: Coloured (42%)
- C_i = city percentage: Indian (1%)
- C_o = city percentage: Other (2%)

- T_w = neighbourhood percentage: White
- T_b = neighbourhood percentage: Black
- T_c = neighbourhood percentage: Coloured
- T_i = neighbourhood percentage: Indian
- T_o = neighbourhood percentage: Other

Land-use composition

Land use is quantified as percentages of the total land use available within that neighbourhood

Public transport

The frequency of stops and stations of The Railway, Myciti Bus Rapid Transit (BRT) and paratransit Minibus Taxi System are aggregated to the scale of the neighbourhood.

Street network configuration

Integration (closeness centrality) of the street network is calculated with angular segment analysis. The mean value for each neighbourhood is statistically correlated against the ND Index. The radii with the strongest correlation is Mean Normalised Integration (NAIN) at Radius n.

Figure 1: Individual Variables Visualised in Neighbourhood Boundaries

4. Results

The optimal number of profiles identified are 4, refer to [Figure 2](#).

Figure 2: Neighbourhood Categories

4.1 Category 1: Affluent and exclusive

Category 1 has a clear spatial geography, located along the base of the mountain and coastline. It is concentrated in wealth but possesses low accessibility both in public transportation and street network configuration. These neighbourhoods are characterised by the lowest average racial heterogeneity and land use which is predominantly residential. An example of a neighbourhood within this category is Camps Bay, nestled between the coastline and mountain, only accessible by motorised vehicles, depicted in [Figure 3](#).

Category 1: Affluent and Exclusive

Figure 3: Category 1 and Camps Bay

4.2 Category 2: Economically disadvantaged and marginalised

Category 2 neighbourhoods are deprived in multiple dimensions and possess the lowest income levels. Their land use is homogenous and access to public transport is low. Many of these neighbourhoods could be likened to the American Ghetto, personified by perpetual segregation and years of disinvestment (Samson, 2019). Langa, an example of a neighbourhood in this category, is bounded by multiple man-made barriers, enclosed in a kind of urban fortress, refer to [Figure 4](#).

Category 2: Economically disadvantaged and marginalised

Figure 4: Category 2 and Langa

4.3 Category 3: Semi residentially integrated, with diverse transport

Category 3 neighbourhoods are principally concentrated in the southern suburbs. Higher average racial heterogeneity is observed alongside increased levels of diverse land use and income. The pronounced difference within this category, is increased access to public transport. *Wynberg*, a typical neighbourhood within Category 3, it is continuously connected to the broader urban fabric by Main Street (Figure 5). The role of streets in attracting people is highlighted in the works of Jacobs (1961) and Gehl (2010).

Category 3: Semi-residentially integrated with diverse transport

Figure 5: Category 3 and Wynberg

4.4 Category 4: Residentially integrated, with diverse land use

Category 4 is the most racially heterogeneous. The two significant indicator divergences are heterogeneous land use and the highest mean closeness centrality out of all the categories. Category 4 reinforces the relation between land use diversity and residential racial heterogeneity. Most Category 4 neighbourhoods are connected to the CBD by Voortrekker Street (Figure 6).

Category 4: Residentially integrated with diverse land use

Figure 6: Category 4

5. Conclusion

Sustainable urban development centred on social inclusion has become a global imperative, and yet it is difficult for cities to implement programs which directly address this issue or even effectively measure or monitor it over time. This study principally makes three contributions:

- 1) Theoretical and empirical motivation for the examination of social inclusion through an urban lens and neighbourhood scale.
- 2) Development of a data driven approach which allows for the identification of associations between multidimensional indicators.
- 3) Identification of categories of neighbourhoods that could be used to support local policies and monitor neighbourhood effects over time.

Access to transport, services, employment, and social opportunities have true social and economic benefits. Communities share these benefits by the virtue of the spatial characteristics of their neighbourhoods. This study presents a quantitative approach for studying social inclusion through an explicitly urban lens based on multi-dimensional indicators. The role of streets as connectors and morphological urban barriers is emphasised. If commitments for creating inclusive cities are to be realised, the use of multi-dimensional, relational, and localised approaches to understand systemic factors that perpetuate social exclusion and segregation within cities is imperative.

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8. Author Biography

Ruth Nelson is a PhD candidate at the faculty of [Technology, Policy and Management](#) in [Delft University of Technology](#) within the Department of [Multi-Actor Systems](#). Ruth holds a Bachelor and Master's degree in Architecture (NMU) and in addition a Masters in Research in Space Syntax: Architecture and Cities (UCL).

Both her practice and research are embedded in system thinking approaches and evidence based methods that draw on data science, urbanism, architecture and sociology. Ruth's principal intentions are to firstly understand the logic of the spatial configuration of different urban environments and then empirically test the effectiveness of proposed design and policy interventions within these contexts. She believes that one of the critical sociological functions of the city is to regulate co-presence among people from different social categories and her research interests are centred on understanding how access to social opportunities and services serve to create more inclusive and sustainable cities.